

**ISOLATION OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS FROM THE PLANT
ACROPTION REPENS L AND STUDY OF THEIR ACARICIDAL
PROPERTIES**

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the theme isolation of phenolic compounds from the plant acroption repens L and study of their acaricidal properties. In addition to this, characteristic features of acroption repens L were discussed and analyzed.

Key words: *antimicrobial properties, Asteraceae family, medicinal plant, perennial plant, phytotoxin, Rhaponticum repens, involucral bracts, monotypic genus.*

Plant chemicals include tannins, terpenoids, alkaloids, and flavonoids. The results of laboratory studies show that these substances have antimicrobial properties. However, the mechanism of action and effectiveness of these plant extracts in most cases have not yet been scientifically confirmed. However, in terms of their chemical, pharmacological, and toxicological effects, the majority of these plants have not been studied yet. Plants have bioactive secondary metabolites and have attracted the attention of scientists due to their complex structure. Scientists are trying to make plant extracts to treat cancer and viral and microbial infections. Plant cytotoxic screening is one of the methods to identify the active compounds of plants. *Acroptilon repens* (Russian knapweed) belong to the Asteraceae family. This plant is perennial herbaceous. Only one species of this plant has been known in Iran, found in West Azarbayjan, Zanjan, and Tehran. *A. repens* is a medicinal

plant with antipyretic properties. *A. repens* is a perennial plant with straight stems up to 80 cm. The branches are broad. The flowers are in the form of flowers. The color of this plant is pink to purple. The common name of this plant is Talkhe, and it is considered a noxious weed. This plant is widely grown in northwestern Iran. The plant is reported to be allelopathic as well as toxic to horses. The genus *Acroptilon* has been the subject of several investigations because of different sesquiterpene lactones and flavones with substantial toxicity. The phytotoxin in the root exudates of *A. repens* has been identified as 7, 8-benzoflavone. *A. repens* has been described as *Centaurea repens* in some literature.

Rhaponticum repens, synonyms including *Acroptilon repens* and *Leuzea repens*, [1] with the common name Russian knapweed, is a species of bushy rhizomatous perennial, up to 80 cm tall. Stems and leaves are finely arachnoid-tomentose becoming glabrous and green with age. The rosette leaves are oblanceolate, pinnately lobed to entire, 2–3 cm wide by 3–8 cm long. The lower cauline leaves are smaller, pinnately lobed; the upper leaves become much reduced, sessile, serrate to entire. The heads are numerous terminating the branches. Flowers are pink to purplish, the marginal ones not enlarged. The outer and middle involucre bracts are broad, striate, smooth with broadly rounded tips; the inner bracts are narrower with hairy tips. Pappus present with bristles 6–11 mm long. Fruit is a whitish, slightly ridged achene. Russian knapweed is a deep-rooted long-lived perennial. Some stands have been in existence for 75 years. It forms dense colonies in cultivated fields, orchards, pastures, and roadsides. A native to Eurasia, Russian knapweed was introduced into North America in the late 19th century. Absent only from southeastern U.S., it has become widespread in other regions, especially in the western United States. [2]

Nigropallidal encephalomalacia, also called chewing disease, a movement disorder similar to Parkinson's disease, is caused in horses ingesting Russian knapweed for prolonged periods. A sesquiterpene lactone, repin, in the plant is

likely responsible for this toxicity. The species was first described by Carl Linnaeus in 1763 as *Centaurea repens*. Augustin Pyramus de Candolle separated it from the genus *Centaurea* in 1838, placing it in the genus *Acroptilon*. The genus name derives from *acro-* (high, here meaning tip) and *ptilo-* (feather).[7] A 1995 molecular phylogenetic study, the structure of the flower, and the chromosome number support separating it from the genus *Centaurea*. Some sources then continue to place it as the sole member of the monotypic genus *Acroptilon*. A phylogenetic study published in 2006 concluded that *Acroptilon* belongs in the genus *Rhaponticum*. Based on the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards recommendations, the antibacterial effects of *Acroptilon* extract and re-fraction were analyzed. The *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 35984 (as gram-positive antibiotic resistance bacteria) strains were used for the test in this research. The effect of extract and fraction on biofilm formation was investigated using the microtiter plate method. To the 50 μ L of nutrient, the broth was inoculated, and 10 μ L of bacteria measuring 0.5 McFarland was placed in each healthy plate and cultured in a concentration lower than the previously determined MBC. Wells containing bacteria-free medium were used as empty. The incubation time of the plates was 24 hours at 37°C. The supernatant was then removed, and each well was thoroughly washed three times with PBS buffer to remove free-floating cells. For 2 minutes at room temperature, it was stained with 200 μ L of Fuchsin biofilm stain. Excess stains were removed by washing the plate with sterile distilled water, and finally, the dye attached to the cells was dissolved by adding 200 μ L of alcohol acetone to each well and shaken for 2 minutes. Absorption was measured at a wavelength of 492 nm using a microplate reader. The following equation was used to estimate the antibiofilm activity of the extract and the given fractions:

$$\text{Antibiofilm activity (\%)} = [1 - (\text{OD}_{\text{Test sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}) / (\text{OD}_{\text{Untreated sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}})] \times 100 [3].$$

All the various fractions and extracts of *A. repens* showed antibacterial activity. The disk diffusion and well diffusion methods are shown in (Table 1). The *A. repens* showed stronger inhibitory activity against *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*, with inhibition zones of 30 and 26 mm, respectively. The ethyl acetate fraction showed the least inhibitory activity against *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*, with inhibition zones of 20 and 19 mm, respectively. The MIC and MBC of ethanolic extract and fractions of *A. repens* are listed in Table 1. The most MIC and MBC were related to the ethanolic extract, and the lowest MIC and MBC were related to water fraction in both *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*. For statistical analysis of the results, as the first step, the normalization of antibacterial effects was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test, which confirmed the normal values. The disk diffusion and well diffusion methods of ethanolic extract and fractions were evaluated by a one-way ANOVA test, which showed a significant difference between the antimicrobial effect of the extract and fractions ($P < 0.0001$).

Phenolic acids are one of the other main phenolic classes within the Plant Kingdom and occur in the form of esters, glycosides or amides, but rarely in free form. Variation in phenolic acids is in the number and location of hydroxyl groups on the aromatic ring [4]. Phenolic acids have two parent structures: hydroxycinnamic and hydroxybenzoic acid. Hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives include ferulic, caffeic, p-coumaric and sinapic acids, while hydroxybenzoic acid derivatives consist of gallic, vanillic, syringic and protocatechuic acids. Another major class of phenolic compounds is the cell wall phenolics. They are insoluble and found in complexes with other types of cell components. The two main groups of cell wall phenolics are lignins and hydroxycinnamic acids. These compounds play a critical role in the cell wall during plant growth by protecting against stresses such as infection, wounding and UV radiation[5]. Tannins can be divided into two groups, hydrolysable tannins and condensed tannins, and have great potential to form oxidative linkages to other plant molecules. Several recent reviews are

available on the characterization of phenolics in foods. Here we review several techniques to extract and analyse plant phenolic compounds. The most important steps for the analysis of phenolic compounds are sample preparation and extraction, followed by classification and quantification using spectrophotometry, gas chromatography (GC), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or capillary electrophoresis (CE) methods.

To conclude all given facts above, it should be noted that ethanolic extract and chloroform, ethyl acetate, and water fraction *A. repens* (L.) DC has antibacterial and antibiotic effects on *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*. This is the first time the antibiofilm activity of ethanolic extract and chloroform, ethyl acetate, and water fraction of *A. repens* has been reported against biofilm formed by *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*. According to the results of the cytotoxic test, ethanolic extract and fractions with increasing concentrations decreased viability. Accordingly, the ethanolic extract and fractions of *A. repens* can be used as a candidate for a new source of medicine for infections caused by *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*.

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